

User Feedback report on the Aurora SDG Research Dashboard

Summary report

AURORA

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

[persistent id to this version: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7646196](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646196)]

Intro

The SDG Aurora Dashboard questionnaire consists of 3 sections: 1) general info; 2) task-based feedback; 3) dashboard experience.

Feedback and suggestion were asked as essential to build and define the design of the characteristics of a highly effective data SDG Dashboard for Aurora.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) provide worldwide guidance for addressing the international community's global challenges. They refer to 17 interlinked global goals to achieve a better and more sustainable future by protecting the natural foundations of life and our planet, ensuring that all human beings can fulfil their potential and live in dignity and prosperity across generations.

SECTION 2 – general info

Participants

Institutions involved

Seven representatives from four institutions completed the survey: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), Federico II di Napoli (UNINA), University of Iceland (UI), Universitat Duisburg-Essen (UDE).

Your Institution
7 risposte

Roles in the institutions

2 Dean and Research manager (VU, UI)

2 Research Impact officer (VU, UDE)

2 Scientists (UNINA)

1 Grant Advisor (UI)

Your role in this Institution

7 risposte

Questions

1. For what purpose would you like to use the SDG dashboard, and why?

To find out about the positioning of VU given SDGs and assess VU's position viz-a-viz other universities in the Netherlands, Europe and elsewhere. A way to assess research impact on the important issue of sustainability, both locally and globally

For strategic reasons and influencing policy affairs at EU level to a) point out the importance of Aurora universities to addressing societal challenges and offering contributions; b) inclusion of Aurora in EU policy-making incl. developing EU programmes; c) establish collaborations with other stakeholders (academia, CSOs, business, national & EU governments) at EU and global level; and d) connecting researchers/research teams because of such collaborations

It is an important tool that supports data tracking and monitoring concerning SDGs . It can enable a broad range of stakeholders to track SDGs performance of UNINA and the whole Aurora Consortium. It can be useful to engage and align all UN and government agencies toward SDGs evidence-based decisions and data insights

Gain and spread awareness

Identify opportunities for collaboration

As evidence and working tool for investigating the relation of research with SDGs in my institution, for societal impact in general.

Searching for the potential to support early-career researchers

2. I think that sustainable development goals play an important role in science

I think that sustainable development goals play an important role in science

7 risposte

SECTION 2 - task-based feedback

This section was completed after participants explored the dashboard by performing the assigned task

3. Which SDG has the highest number of publications within your institute?

Which SDG has the highest number of publications within your institute?

7 risposte

4. How does your institute compare to other institutes within this SDG?

Don't know
It depends on what is related to what. In general, VUA is in the same quadrant as UEA and UA regarding publications quality and use in policy docs.
Not sure
Not sure
Well
This seems to be in line with the nature of the university, as a comprehensive research university, within the group.
good, 2nd place

5. What percentage of these articles is cited by policy documents?

What percentage of these article is cited by policy documents?

7 risposte

6. I think the information acquired in the tasks is relevant for me

I think the information acquired in the tasks is relevant for me

7 risposte

7. It was clear to me how to look for the information

It was clear to me how to look for the information

7 risposte

8. It was difficult to find the required information

It was difficult to find the required information

7 risposte

9. The figures were presenting the relevant information clear to me

The figures were presenting the relevant information clear to me

7 risposte

SECTION 3 dashboard experience

10. There is enough information to get started (e.g., table of contents)

There is enough information to get started (e.g., table of contents)

7 risposte

11. Each of the sections/pages of the dashboard is organized enough

Each of the sections/pages of the dashboard is organized enough

7 risposte

12. The design and the layout of the sections/pages are attractive and interesting

The design and the layout of the sections/pages are attractive and interesting

7 risposte

13. I feel that getting to know the dashboard functionality would have made me more interested in exploring other functionalities on the dashboard

I feel that getting to know the dashboard functionality would have made me more interested in exploring other functionalities on the dashboard

7 risposte

14. Do you have any opinions on the dashboard or suggestions to improve the dashboard that you would like to share?

Make it up to date (Aurora Network is w/o UA and UGA, but includes UP). Would you include CBS? And UPEC? both relate to the alliance...2) the information density on some of the pages is rather high. That makes it less visible at first sight. Indeed needs good attention. Otherwise, it is an interesting tool. What are the other 95% of the publications about? Why can't they be related to any of the SDGs - research too fundamental? 3) How are publications addressing multiple SDGs taken into account (avoiding doublings)? 4) From an EU policy perspective esp. the aggregated level of data is interesting to point out the strength of Aurora. In order to find Aurora experts on certain SDGs or even topics, the tool is indeed interesting. Keep in mind that scientists may move around - check whether they are still at that institution. Their leave may also cause decreased expertise in that university in that field.

zooming in the map could be solved better, currently the steering disappears at a certain zooming factor

15. Would you recommend this dashboard to another person or colleague?

Would you recommend this dashboard to another person or colleague?

7 risposte

16. If yes, please specify why

To follow the example

There are definitely specific interesting elements that can be used for your queries. Think of research support officers and institutional policy officers/international relations officers. Use AURORA WG EU RM and AURORA IC mail group (I can forward your mail - see below)

Good overview

It is fun to work with. I like the new version better. I am still not sure how useful this will be and would like other colleges to have a look.

It shows relevant information in an easy-to-access way

17. Would you like to participate in a second round of interviews to help us improve the dashboard?

Would you like to participate in a second round of interviews to help us improve the dashboard?

7 risposte

People available to be contacted in case of further feedback is needed

.... = removed names for privacy purposes.

....@vu.nl

....@hi.is

....@uni-due.de